

UNICO
I+D 6G

E2.4 Report on requirements for high-precision smart telemetry

v1.2

Publication date: 31/10/2023

[6GENABLERS-AI]

[6GENABLERS]

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión – 6G
I+D**

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

**Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia**

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	6GENABLERS-SP3-L6-P2-E2.4
Líder del PT	OPTARE
Editor Principal	Alberto González Barneo
Contribuyentes	
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación	
PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo	
PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0	Alberto G.B.	Submitted	31/10/2023	Comments by Hatim Chergui
v1.1	Alberto G.B.	Update	23/11/2023	Comments by Hatim Chergui
v1.2	Alberto G.B.	Update	29/11/2023	Comments by Hatim Chergui

Table of Contents

Content

Table of Contents	3
List of Tables	5
List of Figures	6
List of Acronyms	7
Executive Summary	8
1 Introduction.....	9
2 High-Precision Smart Telemetry: State-of-Art Review.....	10
2.1 State of the art.....	10
2.2 Gaps Analysis.....	11
2.3 Gaps in High-Precision Smart Telemetry	11
2.4 Gaps in Intelligent Orchestration.....	12
3 Architecture	13
3.1 General Framework.....	13
3.2 Workflow.....	14
3.2.1 Telemetry at the infrastructure or platform level	14
3.2.2 Traffic level telemetry.....	16
3.2.3 Transport layer level telemetry.....	16
3.2.4 Application-level telemetry.....	17
3.2.5 Orchestration layer and service management flow level telemetry.....	18
4 System Requirements.....	20
4.1 Functional Requirements.....	20
4.1.1 Introduction.....	20
4.1.2 Functional Requirements for Holoportation over 5G/6G Networks.....	21
4.1.3 Advanced Data Collection.....	22
4.1.4 Data Aggregation and Pre-processing	23
4.1.5 Real-time Data Transmission.....	23
4.1.6 Edge Processing	24
4.1.7 Data Storage and Retrieval.....	25
4.1.8 Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies.....	25
4.1.9 Integration with Other Services	26
4.1.10 User Interface and Experience	27
4.1.11 Security and Compliance	27
4.2 Non-Functional Requirements	28

4.2.1	Scalability	29
4.2.2	Interoperability	30
4.2.3	Modularity.....	30
4.2.4	Quality assessment	31
4.2.5	Content Visual quality	32
5	KPIs.....	33
6	Interface definition	37
6.1	Synchronization app collector	37
6.1.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	37
6.1.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	38
6.1.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	38
6.1.4	Architecture	39
6.2	Multi-Sensor Fusion app collector	40
6.2.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	40
6.2.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	41
6.2.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	41
6.2.4	Architecture	42
6.3	Volumetric Video Encoding app collector	42
6.3.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	42
6.3.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	43
6.3.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	43
6.3.4	Architecture	44
6.4	Transport collector	44
6.4.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	44
6.4.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	45
6.4.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	46
6.4.4	Architecture	46
6.5	Network collector	46
6.5.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	47
6.5.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	47
6.5.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	48
6.5.4	Architecture	48
6.6	Platform collector	48
6.6.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API	48
6.6.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	49
6.6.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	49
6.6.4	Architecture	50

6.7	Alarm services	50
6.7.1	OpenTelemetry Metrics API.....	50
6.7.2	OpenTelemetry Tracing API	51
6.7.3	TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services	51
6.7.4	Architecture	52
6.8	Analytics services	52
6.8.1	Overview	52
6.8.2	Architecture	53
6.8.3	Proposal Technologies	53
6.8.4	Adapting to KPIs and Telemetry Data.....	54
6.8.5	Role in decision making.....	54
6.8.6	Integration with Third-Party AI Modules	54
6.8.7	Conclusion.....	55
6.9	KPI & Metrics Manager services	55
6.9.1	Overview	55
6.9.2	Architecture integration.....	56
6.9.3	Integration with Collectors and Services	56
6.9.4	Role in decision making.....	56
6.9.5	Conclusion.....	56
7	Conclusion.....	57

List of Tables

Table 1	Acronyms	7
Table 2	High-precision smart telemetry functional requirements	21
Table 3	Functional Requirements for Holoportation over 5G/6G Networks.....	22
Table 4	Advanced Data Collection	22
Table 5	Data Aggregation and Pre-processing	23
Table 6	Real-time Data Transmission.....	24
Table 7	Edge Processing	24
Table 8	Data Storage and Retrieval.....	25
Table 9	Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies.....	26
Table 10	Integration with Other Services	26
Table 11	User Interface and Experience	27
Table 12	Security and Compliance	28
Table 13	High-precision smart telemetry non-functional requirements.....	29
Table 14	Scalability.....	29

Table 15. Interoperability.....	30
Table 16. Modularity.....	31
Table 17. Quality assessment.....	31
Table 18. Content Visual Quality.....	32
Table 19. Latency.....	33
Table 20. Bandwidth Utilization.....	33
Table 21. Data Synchronization Accuracy.....	34
Table 22. Quality of Experience (QoE).....	34
Table 23. 3D Model Accuracy.....	34
Table 24. Volumetric Video Encoding Efficiency.....	35
Table 25. Resource Allocation Efficiency.....	35
Table 26. AI Model Update and Deployment Time.....	35
Table 27. Network Load and Scalability.....	36
Table 28. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Synchronization app collector.....	38
Table 29. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Synchronization app collector.....	39
Table 30. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Multi-Sensor Fusion app collector.....	40
Table 31. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Multi-sensor Fusion app collector.....	42
Table 32. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Volumetric Video Encoding app collector.....	43
Table 33. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Volumetric Video Encoding app collector.....	44
Table 34. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Transport collector.....	45
Table 35. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Transport collector.....	46
Table 36. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Network collector.....	47
Table 37. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Network collector.....	48
Table 38. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Platform collector.....	49
Table 39. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Platform collector.....	50
Table 40. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Alarm services.....	51
Table 41. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Alarm services.....	52

List of Figures

Figure 1. Predominant challenges for 6G networks.....	11
Figure 2. High-precision smart telemetry diagram.....	13
Figure 3 Workflow chart: Infrastructure Telemetry.....	15
Figure 4 Workflow chart: Traffic Telemetry.....	16
Figure 5 Workflow chart: Transport Telemetry.....	17
Figure 6 Workflow chart: Application Telemetry.....	18
Figure 7 Workflow chart: Orchestration Telemetry.....	19
Figure 8. Synchronization app collector architecture.....	40
Figure 9. Analytics services architecture.....	53
Figure 10. KPI & Metrics Manager services architecture.....	55

List of Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
5G/6G	Fifth/Sixth Generation wireless network
NR	New Radio
Edge	Edge Computing
SaaS	Software-as-a-Service
SNMP	Simple Network Management Protocol
API	Application Programming Interface
SPECS	Specific Transformations
CPU	Central Processing Unit
AIOps	Artificial Intelligence for IT Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
VR	Virtual Reality
IoT	Internet of Things
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
SLS	Service Level Specifications
SLO	Service Level Objectives
QoS	Quality of Service
QoE	Quality of Experience
CNCF	Cloud Native Computing Foundation

Table 1 Acronyms

Executive Summary

This document aims to delineate the indispensable prerequisites for the development of an advanced telemetry system, tailored to empower the holoportation system outlined in the 6GENABLERS-AI initiative. Focused on both functional and non-functional requisites, this elucidation underscores the pivotal role of ultra-automation and optimization within the realm of 6G technologies.

Delivered as part of 6GENABLERS, this document, E2.4, AI for 6G, specifically addresses the system requirements for high-precision intelligent telemetry. It furnishes a comprehensive overview encompassing the contemporary landscape, architectural considerations, intricate system requirements, and interfaces pertinent to the context of 6G. Addressing the evolving dynamics of high-precision intelligent telemetry and orchestration, our emphasis revolves around critical challenges, including ultra-low latency, dynamic adaptability, AI-driven orchestration, efficient network segment management, and rapid resource-based adaptation.

The delineated system requirements serve as the cornerstone for crafting and implementing a telemetry system that ensures seamless, high-fidelity data handling. Each facet is meticulously explored, recognizing the imperatives of high bandwidth, scalability, low latency, and resource optimization. Throughout this exposition, special attention is accorded to the instrumental role played by TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager in upholding performance metrics aligned with industry standards.

In summation, our objective is to establish the framework for an innovative telemetry system that aligns seamlessly with the requirements of 6G. The envisioned outcome is a user experience that not only conforms to but sets new standards in orchestration and high-precision intelligent telemetry, marking a transformative stride in the domain of holoportation.

1 Introduction

The revolution of holographic holoportation has precipitated the emergence of advanced telemetry as a crucial component in conducting immersive interactions across various sectors. As we advance into a new era where telemetry intertwines with holoportation, it is pivotal to explore and deeply understand how these advanced telemetry systems can integrate and optimize to meet the multifaceted demands of this emerging environment.

In this dynamic and rapidly evolving environment, the diversification of components and manufacturers has led to an unprecedented demand for automated mechanisms and telemetry systems, which are not only precise but also efficient and adaptable to different applications and contexts. The motivation for achieving "high precision" in telemetry becomes paramount when considering the intricate requirements of holographic holoportation. The ability to capture, analyze, and transmit data with utmost accuracy is essential for ensuring the seamless synchronization of holographic elements, providing users with an unparalleled and lifelike experience.

Cutting-edge telemetry projects are underway, striving for the unification and design of processes that ensure cohesion and the retrieval of vital data, spanning from infrastructure and network traffic to the transport layer and applications. The integration of a plethora of agents, networks, and administrative domains poses significant challenges and complexities. Thus, it becomes imperative to have robust and detailed telemetry strategies to facilitate network management effectively and automatically, granting detailed network visibility to be able to plan the infrastructure growth and understand how clients use the applications to efficiently implement specific improvements.

2 High-Precision Smart Telemetry: State-of-Art Review

In this section, we analyze the literature on high-precision smart telemetry, identifying the advances and analyzing the existing gaps in terms of technology drivers and their intertwined smart orchestration.

2.1 State of the art

In the realm of next-generation communication technologies, high-precision intelligent telemetry emerges as a defining facet¹. The transition to 6G networks, for example, underscores the value of real-time, complex, and adaptive monitoring solutions².

One study presented an in-depth exploration of in-band network telemetry, shedding light on the need for in-band measurements within a network's operational bandwidth³. This seminal research underscores the importance of timely and accurate measurements, while emphasizing the agility of monitoring in adaptive systems³.

Another prominent paper provides insights into telemetry orchestration in a 5G context⁴. By assigning complex media processing tasks to remote Edge servers, local 5G clients can focus on raw data collection, making efficient use of the 5G NR uplink⁴. This structure not only simplifies client-side processing, but also ensures high-fidelity, latency-efficient telemetry.

Further exploration of telemetry highlights the importance of synchronized frame delivery, especially in scenarios that require teleportation from multiple sources⁵. Proper synchronization can reduce motion misalignments, further optimizing the telemetry experience⁵.

Finally, leveraging cloud-backed functionalities, an advanced telemetry platform introduces adaptive frame buffering along with end-to-end signaling against network uncertainties⁶. These advances are clear indicators of the rapidly evolving nature of telemetry and point to a future where telemetry will not just be a tool but a decision driver in networks.

2.2 Gaps Analysis

Figure 1. Predominant challenges for 6G networks

Predominant challenges are:

- The need for ultra-low latency combined with high bandwidth.
- Dynamic adaptability to network conditions.
- AI-empowered orchestration of telemetry resources.
- Efficient management of network slices.
- Swift adaptation based on resource availability.

2.3 Gaps in High-Precision Smart Telemetry

- **Low latency is paramount.** To achieve the desired accuracy, it is critical to minimize the delay between data capture and processing¹. Advanced algorithms combined with top-tier networks can close this gap.
- Attention also needs to be paid to ensuring the **quality** of the captured telemetry data. Data granularity, resolution and density of captured metrics are critical to ensure that telemetry data is not only abundant, but also valuable².
- Telemetry data can often be voluminous and require **efficient storage** and transmission solutions⁷. Mechanisms need to be developed that offer not only storage solutions but also real-time processing capabilities, rapidly converting raw data into actionable information.
- In addition, ensuring a **standardized approach** to telemetry across various network systems is essential to ensure seamless operability and consistency².

2.4 Gaps in Intelligent Orchestration

Deploying AI in telemetry remains a challenge given the legacy infrastructures of existing systems⁷. This barrier can potentially be circumvented with the introduction of standardized AI interfaces designed for telemetry.

In addition, real-time adaptation based on changing telemetry needs is paramount. As systems grow and adapt, so do their telemetry requirements⁸. Orchestrating resources in such a dynamic environment requires a robust, adaptable and forward-looking system.

In summary, while advances have been made in high-precision intelligent telemetry, there are a host of challenges and gaps to address. Addressing them will pave the way to an era in which telemetry is not just a complementary tool but a core component of advanced networks².

¹Mohammed Banafaa, Ibraheem Shayea, Jafri Din, Marwan Hadri Azmi, Abdulaziz Alashbi, Yousef Ibrahim Daradkeh, Abduraqeb Alhammadi, "6G Mobile Communication Technology: Requirements, Targets, Applications, Challenges, Advantages, and Opportunities".

²Taleb, T., Aguiar, R. L., Yahia, I. G. B., Chatras, B., Christensen, G., Chunduri, U., Clemm, A., Costa, X., Dong, L., Elmirghani, J., Yosuf, B., Foukas, X., Galis, A., Giordani, M., Gurtov, A., Hecker, A., Huang, C.-W., Jacquenet, C., Kellerer, W., Zorzi, M. (2020). *White Paper on 6G Networking* [White paper]. (6G Research Visions, No. 6). University of Oulu.

³Shihabur Rahman Chowdhury, Raouf Boutaba, Jérôme François. LINT: Accuracy-adaptive and Lightweight In-band Network Telemetry. IM 2021 - 17th IFIP/IEEE International Symposium on Integrated Network Management, May 2021, Bordeaux / Virtual, France.

⁴Michael Dieudonne, Hua Wang, Whitepaper Beyond 5G/6G KPIs and Target Values.

⁵K. Samdanis and T. Taleb, "The Road beyond 5G: A Vision and Insight of the Key Technologies," in *IEEE Network*, vol. 34, no. 2, pp. 135-141, March/April 2020, doi: 10.1109/MNET.001.1900228.

⁶X. Xu, Y. Pan, P. P. M. Y. Lwin and X. Liang, "3D holographic display and its data transmission requirement," 2011 International Conference on Information Photonics and Optical Communications, Jurong West, Singapore, 2011, pp. 1-4, doi: 10.1109/IPOC.2011.6122872.

⁷Manzanares-Lopez, Pilar et al. "Passive In-Band Network Telemetry Systems: The Potential of Programmable Data Plane on Network-Wide Telemetry." *IEEE Access* 9 (2021): 20391-20409.

⁸Minling Lai, Huiling Tang, Qilin Bi, Yanyao Guo, Zhengyu Tang, Xinhong Zen, Junkeng Ding, Spatial feature point measurement on large-curved surfaces: A portable mobile measurement method based on monocular multi-angle points, *Alexandria Engineering Journal*.

3 Architecture

3.1 General Framework

The architecture is structured into modular components and provided as a Software-as-a-Service (SaaS), including interface components or connectors, which would provide access to different communication protocols adapted to the indicated telemetry levels (from SNMP and sFlow to Rest API), the SPECs or cartridges with the necessary transformations on the data based on the possible different vendors, and the service or function layer, which implements these modules and will be divided by layer, allowing this level to have the abstraction capability over the data necessary to be processed by the rest of the platform's functionalities.

Figure 2. High-precision smart telemetry diagram

For this, different layers or levels associated with this capability will be established, and, as a proposal, they will be the following:

- Telemetry at the **infrastructure or platform** level (physical or virtual nodes where the different functions or applications are deployed).
- **Traffic** level telemetry of the different networks, physical or virtual.
- **Transport** layer level telemetry.
- **Application**-level telemetry.
- Telemetry at the **orchestration** layer and service management flow level.

Once the telemetry events collected by the acquisition layer are received and processed, they are made available to the rest of the platform through the elements of the backend layer, in which the collected event streams will be dumped to persistence services, optimized both for the management of time series and for the management of traces and meta-information related to the collected telemetry, through the broker that will, on the other hand, enable services deployed in the analysis layer to access them in real-time.

This comprehensive approach allows for efficient management of telemetry data from its acquisition to its analysis and storage. Subsequently, the workflows associated with this telemetry process will be described in detail, providing a clearer view of each component and its role in the ecosystem of modern telemetry.

3.2 Workflow

3.2.1 Telemetry at the infrastructure or platform level

The outlined diagram illustrates an interactive workflow within a system equipped with high-precision smart telemetry. This workflow begins with the 'User' making a request to 'Edge'.

Once 'Edge' receives this request, it activates and begins to measure and record various metrics, such as CPU usage, memory usage, storage usage, network latency between the user and 'Edge', and other relevant aspects. Subsequently, 'Edge' sends these metrics to 'High-Precision Smart Telemetry', which in turn, sends an acknowledgment to 'Edge'.

The workflow continues with 'Edge' forwarding the original request to 'Cloud'. Like 'Edge', 'Cloud' also measures and records pertinent metrics, which are then sent to 'High-Precision Smart Telemetry', receiving an acknowledgment as well.

Finally, once 'Cloud' has processed the request, it sends a response to 'Edge'. 'Edge' processes this response, measuring and recording the latency of processing the response, and then sends these final metrics to 'High-Precision Smart Telemetry' before sending the final response to the 'User'.

Figure 3 Workflow chart: Infrastructure Telemetry

3.2.2 Traffic level telemetry

The user initiates the process with a request received by the edge node, activating an application to handle it. The application then forwards the request through the network, measuring metrics like latency, jitter, and throughput. These metrics provide a comprehensive assessment of the network's state.

The request reaches the cloud, where a high-precision telemetry component processes and acknowledges the network metrics, offering real-time insights. A response is generated and sent back to the user, completing the request-response cycle. This flow emphasizes meticulous tracking and effective management at each interaction step.

Figure 4 Workflow chart: Traffic Telemetry

3.2.3 Transport layer level telemetry.

The illustrated sequence diagram provides a cohesive depiction of interactions within the transport layer, a pivotal component in network communication. The sequence initiates with the User establishing a connection with the Edge, serving as a catalyst for a series of interactions within the system. Upon activation, the Edge communicates with the Transport layer to establish a connection, highlighting the role of the Transport layer in facilitating communication between network entities. During this phase, the Transport layer measures and records essential metrics such as Connection Establishment Time, Connection Termination Time, Retransmission Rate, and Window Size, ensuring optimal data transmission and network performance.

Post-establishment of the connection, the Transport layer forwards the gathered metrics to High-Precision Smart Telemetry, emphasizing the interplay between network communication and real-time monitoring. The Telemetry, upon receiving the metrics, sends an acknowledgment back to the Transport layer, confirming the receipt of the metrics and enabling a continuous flow of information.

Finally, the Transport layer engages with the Cloud, transmitting data and establishing another touchpoint in the communication sequence. The Cloud acknowledges the receipt of the data, sustaining the information flow within the system. The acknowledgment from the Cloud triggers the Transport layer to confirm the transmission to the Edge.

Figure 5 Workflow chart: Transport Telemetry

3.2.4 Application-level telemetry.

The sequence begins when the User sends a request to the Edge system, triggering the process within this system. Upon receiving the request, the Edge system starts to measure and record specific metrics, such as response time, computing utilization, and data integrity, along with frame-per-second metrics, server-side perceived throughput per second, and frame delay, for the deployed applications, including sync, multi-sensor fusion, and volumetric video encoding.

After the metric collection, the Edge system sends these metrics to High-Precision Smart Telemetry, after processing the receipt of the metrics, issues a receipt acknowledgment back to the Edge system, informing it that the metrics have been successfully received. Following this, if necessary, the Edge system interacts with the Cloud system to carry out additional operations or gather more information. The Cloud, in turn, responds to the Edge system after completing the requested operations or providing the required information.

Finally, the Edge system formulates a response based on the information and metrics collected and processed and sends it to the User. With the successful delivery of the response to the User, the Edge system concludes its activation, and the sequence comes to an end.

Figure 6 Workflow chart: Application Telemetry

3.2.5 Orchestration layer and service management flow level telemetry.

In this sequence diagram, a flow of interaction is portrayed amongst various components, including an Orchestrator, an Edge system, a Cloud system, "High-Precision Smart Telemetry," and AIOps.

The sequence initiates with AIOps sending a trigger to the Orchestrator to deploy new models, activating the process within the Orchestrator. Subsequently, the Orchestrator dispatches instructions to the Edge system to deploy or manage an application. Upon receiving this directive, the Edge system becomes active and starts to measure and record metrics related to the deployment's success or failure, resource allocation, and scaling events.

Subsequently, the Edge system transmits the orchestration-related metrics to "High-Precision Smart Telemetry," which, after processing these received metrics, sends an acknowledgement back to the Edge system, indicating the successful receipt of the metrics.

Simultaneously, AIOps also sends specific metrics, related to model optimization, time to retraining, and API calls for AI as a service, to "High-Precision Smart Telemetry." This component, after recording and processing these additional metrics, sends an

acknowledgment to AIOps, thereby concluding the interaction with both, the Edge system and AIOps.

Meanwhile, the Orchestrator also interacts with the Cloud system to manage resources in the cloud. The Cloud responds to the Orchestrator with an acknowledgment or status, providing feedback regarding the resource management state. Finally, once the response from the Cloud is received, the Orchestrator deactivates the interaction with the Cloud.

Figure 7 Workflow chart: Orchestration Telemetry

4 System Requirements

This section describes both the functional and non-functional requirements of the high-precision smart telemetry system.

4.1 Functional Requirements

Functional requirements refer to a set of specifications that outline the tasks that a system must be capable of performing, as well as the way in which those tasks should be carried out. These specifications define the functions, features, and abilities that are essential for a system or software application to satisfy the requirements of its users.

4.1.1 Introduction

For a high-precision intelligent telemetry system, these functionalities not only determine the system's core operations but also dictate how the system interacts with the dynamically evolving this kind of networks landscape. From real-time data collection to predictive analytics, these requirements represent the foundational pillars, ensuring that the telemetry system can proactively and effectively manage, monitor, and optimize next-generation networks.

In this initial section, our focus will be on providing a holistic view of generic functional requirements, establishing a foundational understanding. By first gaining insight into these universal principles, we can subsequently tailor this knowledge to our specific context. In that order, we present some of them:

Functional Requirement	Description
Real-time Data Collection	Capability to collect data in real-time from multiple network nodes.
Data Aggregation	Aggregation of data from various sources in a unified manner.
Predictive Analysis	Ability to predict network anomalies or failures before they occur.
Automated Decision Making	Use AI to make automated decisions for network adjustments based on telemetry data.
Network Self-healing	Automate the healing process in case of any network disruptions.
Data Retention and History	Store telemetry data for analysis and historical trends.

User Interface	Visualization tools for operators to view real-time and historical network performance data.
Alerts and Notifications	Real-time alerts for any anomalies or disruptions.

Table 2. High-precision smart telemetry functional requirements

4.1.2 Functional Requirements for Holoportation over 5G/6G Networks

Having established a foundational understanding of generic functional requirements, it's crucial to adapt and contextualize these to our unique and innovative scenario: Holoportation over 5G/6G Networks.

Holoportation, a cutting-edge technology, leverages the unparalleled speed and low latency of 5G and 6G networks to deliver real-time 3D holographic projections of individuals from one location to another. This is not merely the next step in video communication; it's a quantum leap.

Following this, in the subsequent sections, we will deep dive into how these generic functional requirements take shape and specificity in the realm of holoportation over next-generation networks. By doing so, we aim to provide a precise and comprehensive understanding of the system's expected behavior tailored to this transformative application.

Functional Requirement	Description
Advanced Data Collection	Real-time 3D data capture from sensors, ensuring accurate preliminary holographic output.
Data Aggregation and Pre-processing	Consolidation and synchronization of sensor data streams, preparing data for optimized transmission.
Real-time Data Transmission	Swift and consistent transfer of holographic data, prioritizing high bandwidth and low latency.
Automated Decision Making	Use AI to make automated decisions for network adjustments based on telemetry data.
Edge Processing	Offloads heavy tasks to the network's edge, enhancing real-time processing and resource management.
Data Storage and Retrieval	Secure storage and prompt retrieval of holographic data in optimized formats.
Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies	Monitoring for irregularities, ensuring consistent holographic experiences.

Integration with Other Services	Combines holoportation with services like video conferencing for enriched user interactions.
User Interface and Experience	Front-end tools for clear and interactive 3D content viewing with enhanced user engagement.
Security and Compliance	Protection of holoportation data from breaches, maintaining data integrity and regulatory adherence.

Table 3. Functional Requirements for Holoportation over 5G/6G Networks

4.1.3 Advanced Data Collection

Overview

In the field of holoportation, the quality, accuracy and real-time capabilities of data collection are paramount. Advanced data collection is the fundamental building block, ensuring that the resulting holographic representations are not only accurate but also realistic and immersive. The 5G/6G infrastructure provides the bandwidth and low latency necessary to support this high-fidelity data transmission.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Real-time Data Processing	As data is captured, initial processing is crucial. This could include filtering out noise, adjusting for ambient light conditions, and compressing the initial data.	Ensuring that this processing is done in real time without introducing noticeable latency.
Integration with 5G/6G Infrastructure	Captured data must be transmitted immediately for further processing. Integration with the 5G/6G network ensures that this transmission is fast and reliable.	Ensure constant bandwidth availability, especially in areas with network congestion or fluctuating signal strength.

Table 4. Advanced Data Collection

Conclusion

Advanced data collection for holoportation over 5G/6G networks is not just about capturing data; it is about ensuring that the data is of the highest quality, captured in real time and ready for later stages of the holoportation process. The challenges are manifold, but with the right technology and integration with robust 5G/6G infrastructure, realistic and immersive holographic experiences can be achieved.

4.1.4 Data Aggregation and Pre-processing

Overview

After initial data collection, holoportation requires meticulous fusion and preliminary refinement of this data. This stage consolidates the input from multiple sensors into a singular, cohesive data set ready for further processing and transmission. The overall challenge is to ensure data integrity, synchronization, and optimization, especially when catering to real-time scenarios enhanced by 5G/6G capabilities.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Data Filtering	Removal of noise and irrelevant data. This could include ambient noise, background objects or transient interference.	Distinguishing between genuine data and noise, especially when dealing with intricate details or subtle movements.
Data Compression	Given the large volume of holoportation data, initial compression is essential prior to transmission, ensuring efficient use of bandwidth without compromising quality.	Apply lossless compression techniques that preserve data fidelity while achieving a significant reduction in data size.

Table 5. Data Aggregation and Pre-processing

Conclusion

Data aggregation and preprocessing form the bridge between raw sensor data and a refined, cohesive holographic representation. Achieving perfection at this stage is crucial to ensure that subsequent stages, from transmission to final hologram representation, are seamless and accurate. With the capabilities of 5G/6G networks, these processes can be accelerated, but the inherent challenges of data integrity, synchronization and optimization remain fundamental to this phase.

4.1.5 Real-time Data Transmission

Overview

Fast and reliable holoportation data transfer is crucial to maintaining the immersive and interactive quality of the experience. Real-time data transmission ensures that the voluminous 3D data generated during holoportation is delivered efficiently and quickly to users' devices over 5G/6G networks, while minimizing latency and ensuring high bandwidth.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Data Compression and Optimization	It is essential to optimize data for efficient transmission while maintaining quality. This includes effective compression techniques adapted to 3D data.	Achieving a balance between reducing data size and maintaining high fidelity holographic representations.
Dynamic Quality Adaptation	The system must be able to dynamically adjust data quality according to available network resources and user device capabilities.	Implement adaptive transmission and encoding to adapt to the user's network conditions and device capabilities in real time.

Table 6. Real-time Data Transmission

Conclusion

Real-time data transmission is the backbone of holoportation, ensuring that immersive 3D data is delivered quickly and seamlessly to user devices. The challenges lie in balancing bandwidth demands, minimizing latency, and maintaining data quality under various network conditions. Leveraging the capabilities of 5G/6G networks is critical to achieving these goals and providing users with a compelling holoportation experience.

4.1.6 Edge Processing

Overview

Edge processing, in the context of holoportation, involves handling and refining holoportation data closer to its source or user, rather than in centralized data centers. Given the immense computational demands of real-time holoportation, edge processing offloads these loads from user devices, optimizing performance and ensuring real-time interactivity.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Real-time Data Analysis and Refinement	Edge nodes can perform real-time analysis, refining data before it is transmitted or presented to the user.	Implement fast analysis algorithms designed for 3D holoportation data.
Localized Data storage	Temporary storage of holoport data at the edge can ensure faster retrieval and improved responsiveness during interactive sessions.	Implement fast data storage and retrieval solutions tailored to large-scale 3D data.

Table 7. Edge Processing

Conclusion

Edge Processing serves as a key enabler in the holoportation process, providing the necessary computational power right where it is most crucial. This proximity-driven approach ensures that holoportation remains seamless, responsive, and immersive, leveraging the enhanced capabilities of 5G/6G networks. While challenges exist, the fusion of edge computing with holoportation promises transformative experiences that blur the lines between virtual and real worlds.

4.1.7 Data Storage and Retrieval

Overview

The voluminous nature of holoportation data requires efficient storage and retrieval mechanisms. Beyond simply accommodating large data sets, the system must ensure fast access, maintain data integrity, and support data versioning to enrich the holoportation experience.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
High-capacity Storage	Given the immense volume of 3D holographic data, storage systems must be prepared to handle terabytes or even petabytes of data.	Scalability of storage infrastructure to meet growing demands without performance degradation.
Data Integrity and Redundancy	Ensure that stored holoportation data remains uncorrupted and readily available, even in the face of hardware failure.	Establish reliable backup and redundancy mechanisms designed for voluminous holographic data.

Table 8. Data Storage and Retrieval

Conclusion

Data storage and retrieval in the holoportation domain is not simply about accommodating large data sets; it is about ensuring that this data is available, consistent, and in the best format to deliver real-time holographic experiences. With the capabilities of 5G/6G networks, storage and access speeds can be optimized, but the fundamental challenges of handling massive volumes of 3D data in a dynamic environment remain.

4.1.8 Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies

Overview

In real-time systems such as holoport, rapid anomaly detection is paramount. Whether it's a problem in data transmission or a potential security breach, instant alerts and notifications ensure that problems are quickly detected and rectified, preserving the immersive holoportation experience.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
User-configurable Alert Parameters	Allow users or network administrators to customize alert thresholds or preferences according to specific needs.	Design an intuitive interface for alert customization without compromising the default alert sensitivity of the system.
Multi-channel Notification Delivery	Sending alerts through multiple channels, such as SMS, email, dashboard notifications or even voice alerts for critical issues.	Implement robust delivery mechanisms that ensure alerts are received, even during network congestion or outages.

Table 9. Alerts and Notifications for Anomalies

Conclusion

Alerts and notifications serve as the first line of defense to maintain the fidelity and reliability of holoportation experiences. With the enhanced capabilities and demands of 5G/6G networks, these alerting systems must be hyper-reactive, intelligent, and user-centric, ensuring that anomalies are not only detected but preemptively addressed where possible.

4.1.9 Integration with Other Services

Overview

Given the expansive and interconnected nature of modern digital infrastructures, holoportation does not operate in isolation. It is essential to integrate seamlessly with various ancillary services, such as video conferencing, cloud storage or security protocols, to deliver a holistic and enriching user experience.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Seamless Video Conferencing Integration	Combining holoportation with conventional videoconferencing systems can extend their utility, enabling a combination of 2D and 3D communication.	Achieve synchronicity between traditional video transmissions and 3D holographic data while ensuring consistent quality.
Cloud Service Linkages	Integration with cloud platforms can facilitate big data storage, high-speed processing, and real-time access for holoportation.	Manage data transfer speeds, ensure data security during transmission, and coordinate between perimeter processing and centralized cloud operations.

Table 10. Integration with Other Services

Conclusion

The integration of holoporting with other services is a testament to its multifaceted nature in the modern digital ecosystem. These integrations not only enhance its core functionality but also broaden its applicability. As 5G/6G networks foster interconnectivity, ensuring seamless service integrations in holoportation will be critical to its widespread adoption and success.

4.1.10 User Interface and Experience

Overview

At the forefront of user interaction, the interface of holoportation platforms should be intuitive, responsive, and immersive. Beyond simple visual appeal, the UI/UX should facilitate navigation, personalization and provide real-time feedback, ensuring that users can maximize the potential of holoportation without steep learning curves.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Immersive 3D Interfaces	The user interface should complement the 3D nature of holoportation, providing an interactive and spatially aware environment for users.	Design an interface that feels natural in a 3D space, balancing immersion and functionality.
Customizability and User Profiles	Catering to diverse user preferences, the user interface should allow for customization, from aesthetic themes to functional widgets.	Design a flexible interface without overwhelming novice users.

Table 11. User Interface and Experience

Conclusion

The user interface and user experience are the gateway through which users interact with the wonders of holoportation. It's not just about aesthetics; it's about creating an environment that resonates with users' needs, expectations, and realities. As 5G/6G networks enable richer holoportation experiences, the onus is on UI/UX design to make these experiences accessible, enjoyable, and transformative.

4.1.11 Security and Compliance

Overview

As holoportation becomes more prevalent, ensuring robust security and compliance with regulatory standards becomes critical. Both user data and the holoportation process itself need protection against potential threats, and systems must operate within established legal and ethical boundaries.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
End-to-End Encryption	Each piece of holoportation data, whether in transit or at rest, must be encrypted, ensuring that it is protected from prying eyes.	Implement encryption mechanisms that do not introduce significant latency, preserving real-time communication.
User Authentication and Authorization	Before users can holoport, they must undergo a secure authentication process. Authorization levels may differ according to user roles.	Establish multi-factor authentication mechanisms that are secure and easy to use.

Table 12. Security and Compliance

Conclusion

The dynamic scope of holoportation, facilitated by 5G/6G networks, generates unprecedented communication capabilities. However, with great power comes great responsibility. Ensuring that these experiences are not only immersive but also secure and compliant is imperative for widespread adoption and trust. As the line between virtual and physical continues to blur, so does the need for vigilant, robust and adaptable security measures.

4.2 Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements are a set of specifications that detail the characteristics, attributes, and qualities of a system or software application, as opposed to its specific functional capabilities. These requirements pertain to the general performance, quality, and usability of the system or software application, rather than its functionalities and features.

The non-functional requirements of the use-case are listed as follows:

Non-Functional Requirement	Description
Scalability	The implementation of the use case should be scalable and allow for the automatic admission of multiple concurrent AR users/sessions/slices without modifying the architecture.
Interoperability	The setup of the use case should be interoperable with any type of user device/AR kit
Modularity	The implementation should be modular primarily in such a way the upgrade of one component can be independently done

	without affecting the other components.
Quality assessment	The Holoportation platform SHOULD be able to evaluate the expected quality of experience according to the objective metrics
Content visual quality	The Holoportation platform MUST support playback of end-user's representation of at least 960x540 pixels

Table 13 High-precision smart telemetry non-functional requirements

4.2.1 Scalability

Overview

Scalability is a fundamental non-functional requirement for holoport systems. As this innovative technology evolves, it must adapt seamlessly to expanding user bases, increasing data loads and technological advances.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
User scalability	The holoport system must scale appropriately to accommodate an increasing number of concurrent users without degrading performance.	The system must be able to serve a user base ranging from individual users to large organisations without performance bottlenecks.
Load Balancing and Resource Allocation	As demand fluctuates, the system must dynamically distribute loads among servers and allocate resources efficiently.	The system must optimise resource allocation for real-time holoportation while maintaining low latency.

Table 14. Scalability

Conclusion

The dynamic scope of holoportation, facilitated by 5G/6G networks, generates unprecedented communication capabilities. However, with great power comes great responsibility. Ensuring that these experiences are not only immersive but also secure and compliant is imperative for widespread adoption and trust. As the line between virtual and physical continues to blur, so does the need for vigilant, robust and adaptable security measures.

4.2.2 Interoperability

Overview

Interoperability is a critical non-functional requirement for holoport systems. It ensures that the technology can communicate and function seamlessly with multiple external devices, networks and systems, promoting a cohesive and connected holoportation experience.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Device Interoperability	Holoportation systems should work effortlessly with a wide range of devices, including AR glasses, VR headsets, smartphones, and traditional displays.	The system must recognise and adapt to the capabilities and specifications of different devices, ensuring consistent performance and functionality.
Integration with Third-Party Services	Holoport systems are often integrated with external services such as video conferencing, cloud storage or IoT platforms. It is essential that these integrations work without problems.	The system must have well-defined APIs and protocols to interact with third-party services, ensuring data flow and integration of functionalities.

Table 15. Interoperability

Conclusion

Interoperability is critical to the success of holoporting. It allows users to seamlessly transition between external devices, networks, and services, ensuring a cohesive and integrated holoport experience. As technology advances and diversifies, interoperability becomes an essential requirement.

4.2.3 Modularity

Overview

Modularity is a key non-functional requirement for holoport systems. It ensures that the system is designed in such a way that its components can be easily upgraded or replaced without disrupting the entire system. This flexibility is vital to adapt to evolving technologies and requirements.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Component-Based Design	Holoport systems must be built from separate, interchangeable modules or components. These components may include data collection, processing, representation, and user interface.	Each module should function independently, allowing isolated upgrades or replacements without affecting the entire system.
Open APIs and Protocols	The system must employ open APIs and communication protocols, allowing third-party integrations, custom extensions, and enhanced compatibility with future technologies.	Open APIs should be well documented and easily accessible for developers to create new modules or integrate external services.

Table 16. Modularity

Conclusion

Modularity is essential in holoportation systems as it ensures that the technology can keep pace with rapidly evolving holoportation techniques, new hardware and changing user preferences. By breaking the system into discrete, replaceable components, it becomes adaptable, upgradeable, and versatile.

4.2.4 Quality assessment

Overview

Quality assessment is a critical non-functional requirement for holoportation systems. It ensures that the system consistently delivers high quality immersive experiences to users, while allowing for continuous monitoring and improvement.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Real-time Performance Monitoring	Holoportation systems must have mechanisms for real-time monitoring of performance metrics, including latency, frame rate, and data integrity.	The system must continuously assess performance and immediately detect and address issues that may affect the quality of the holoportation experience.
User Experience Evaluation	The user experience should be systematically evaluated to ensure that users are satisfied with the quality of the holoport sessions.	User feedback and metrics related to user interaction, comfort and satisfaction should guide system improvements.

Table 17. Quality assessment

Conclusion

Quality assessment is vital for holoportation systems to provide users with a consistently high quality and immersive experience. It involves real-time monitoring, user feedback, data quality control and performance optimisation. Continuous evaluation and improvement are essential for a successful holoport service.

4.2.5 Content Visual quality

Overview

Content Visual Quality is a crucial non-functional requirement for holoportation systems. It ensures that 3D holographic content produced and rendered during holoportation sessions meets high standards of visual fidelity and realism.

Requirements	Description	Challenge
Holographic Rendering Fidelity	Holoportation systems shall render 3D holographic content with high fidelity, ensuring that virtual objects or individuals appear realistic and lifelike.	The system should minimise artefacts, pixelation and discrepancies in the rendering process.
Resolution and Clarity	The visual quality of holoport content should be characterised by high resolution and clarity. Users should perceive fine details in holographic representations.	The system shall support high resolution displays and maintain visual clarity even during fast movements.

Table 18. Content Visual Quality

Conclusion

Content visual quality is essential for holoportation systems to create a truly immersive and realistic experience for users. High standards of rendering fidelity, resolution, colour accuracy and other visual aspects contribute to a captivating and believable holoportation experience.

5 KPIs

In the burgeoning landscape of advanced network technologies, holoportation is at the forefront, promising unprecedented user experiences and revolutionizing virtual presence. As 6G technologies develop, they have the potential to support latency-sensitive, data-intensive applications by offering increased bandwidth, reduced latency, and superior edge computing capabilities. However, as with any evolving technology, there is an inherent challenge in ensuring seamless performance and top-tier quality of experience (QoE) for users.

Key performance indicators (KPIs) emerge as beacons in this uncharted territory. By defining, monitoring, and analyzing these metrics, we can measure the status, effectiveness, and efficiency of holoport systems in real time. Moreover, they form the foundation upon which performance management, system optimization and resource orchestration revolve.

This section delves into the intricate web of KPIs essential for holoportation, laying out a blueprint for their effective implementation.

KPI	Latency
Description	Refers to the time delay from when a data packet is sent to when it's received.
Importance	Critical for real-time interaction in holoportation. High latency can disrupt the user experience, causing delays or misalignments in holographic displays.
Threshold	Maximum allowable latency of 10ms.
Measurement Method	Monitor and record data transmission times between the sender (sensors) and the receiver (viewer).

Table 19. Latency

KPI	Bandwidth Utilization
Description	The rate of data transfer over the network.
Importance	Ensures seamless transmission of holographic content, which is data-intensive.
Threshold	Minimum required bandwidth of 50Mbps for a single hologram.
Measurement Method	Use network monitoring tools to gauge real-time data transfer rates.

Table 20. Bandwidth Utilization

KPI	Data Synchronization Accuracy
Description	The system's ability to ensure data from multiple sources is aligned in time.
Importance	Ensures the integrity of the holographic display by avoiding motion misalignment.
Threshold	Maximum motion misalignment of 100ms.
Measurement Method	Monitor frame arrival times from multiple sensors and compare discrepancies.

Table 21. Data Synchronization Accuracy

KPI	Quality of Experience (QoE)
Description	User's perceived quality of the holoportation experience..
Importance	Ensuring a high processing capacity is vital for maintaining real-time holoportation experiences, especially during peak usage times.
Threshold	At least 90% positive feedback on user experience surveys.
Measurement Method	Surveys, feedback systems, or real-time monitoring of user interactions.

Table 22. Quality of Experience (QoE)

KPI	3D Model Accuracy
Description	Precision and fidelity of the transmitted 3D models.
Importance	Directly impacts the realism and quality of holoportation..
Threshold	Less than 5% deviation from the original 3D model's accuracy.
Measurement Method	Compare the transmitted model with the original capture using software analysis tools.

Table 23. 3D Model Accuracy

KPI	Volumetric Video Encoding Efficiency
Description	Efficiency of encoding 3D data into video formats.
Importance	Determines the speed and quality of holoportation content display.
Threshold	Compression ratio of at least 4:1 without significant loss of quality.
Measurement Method	Analyze encoded video data for size, speed, and data fidelity.

Table 24. Volumetric Video Encoding Efficiency

KPI	Resource Allocation Efficiency
Description	Effectiveness of AIOps-enabled orchestration in allocating resources.
Importance	Optimal allocation ensures reduced latency and improved overall performance.
Threshold	Maximum 10% resource wastage during peak load.
Measurement Method	Monitor resource utilization metrics in real-time across the network.

Table 25. Resource Allocation Efficiency

KPI	AI Model Update and Deployment Time
Description	Time taken to update and deploy AI models in the AIOps framework.
Importance	Ensures swift response to changing service dynamics.
Threshold	Model updates and deployments should be under 2 hours.
Measurement Method	Track the complete lifecycle of AI model updates from training to deployment.

Table 26. AI Model Update and Deployment Time

KPI	Network Load and Scalability
Description	The infrastructure's ability to handle increasing user demands without performance drops.
Importance	Ensures the system can scale without compromising user experience.
Threshold	System should scale to handle a 50% increase in user demand without more than a 10% drop in performance.
Measurement Method	Use stress testing tools and monitor performance metrics during peak load scenarios.

Table 27. Network Load and Scalability

6 Interface definition

In the field of high-precision intelligent telemetry, interfaces serve as bridges connecting complex architectural components. Their role is paramount: they facilitate a smooth flow of data, ensure efficiency, and support the effectiveness of the holoport process. Through these interfaces, the granularity of real-time metrics and performance indicators is not only acquired but also effectively channeled.

To ensure the accuracy and reliability of these interfaces, we have integrated two industry-leading solutions: OpenTelemetry and TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager. **OpenTelemetry**, an observability framework for cloud-native software, offers the ability to collect telemetry data from our various subsystems, aligning it with our detailed interface definitions, such as synchronization, multi-sensor fusion and more. Its capabilities enable consistent, high-quality data collection, ensuring a rich set of insights.

TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager is an established standard in performance management. Its integration within our architecture helps ensure that performance metrics derived from our interfaces align with industry standards and best practices. From traffic level telemetry to orchestration layer assessments, the TM Forum framework ensures a comprehensive and standardized approach to performance management.

As we delve deeper, this section clarifies the nuances of these interfaces, emphasizing their integral role within the system and establishing their symbiotic relationship with the KPIs they inherently influence. Furthermore, in the subsections that follow, we will detail how we leverage the power and capabilities of OpenTelemetry and the TM Forum framework, ensuring that its utilities are fully realized across our interface spectrum. So, dig deeper to understand how each interface anchors specific aspects of the holoport experience and the KPIs that underline its performance.

6.1 Synchronization app collector

The collector is vital, ensuring real-time telemetry data for frame synchronization. OpenTelemetry is crucial, offering APIs for tracking frame journeys, detecting misalignments, and providing flexibility in capturing metrics. TM Forum's Performance Manager strengthens the collector by aligning performance metrics with industry standards. Metrics include frame transfer delay, processing delay, misaligned/delayed frames count, synchronization accuracy, and service uptime. The Tracing API ensures data accuracy in a distributed system, maintaining synchronization order. TM Forum's services, such as Service Quality Management and Performance Thresholding APIs, set benchmarks, monitor thresholds, and provide real-time alerts. The architecture ensures seamless data flow from raw telemetry to actionable metrics.

6.1.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

The OpenTelemetry Metrics API serves as a fundamental tool in telemetry data collection, enabling accurate and contextually relevant metrics across diverse systems. For the collector of timing applications, it is a beacon that sheds light on the intricate dynamics of frame timing. As we explore further, we will detail specific metrics and tools and how they reinforce our commitment to seamless data synchronization.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Frame Transfer Delay	Histogram	Time taken for a frame to be transferred from one point to another.	Monitors transfer speeds and alerts for any delays.
Frame Synchronization Accuracy	Gauge (Captures current values)	Percentage of frames that are synchronized perfectly within the set threshold.	Ensures accuracy in frame synchronization.

Table 28. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Synchronization app collector

6.1.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

The modern distributed system requires a high degree of observability to ensure data accuracy, especially when synchronizing key performance indicators (KPIs). The OpenTelemetry Tracing API provides essential components to efficiently monitor, track and synchronize data.

- **Span:** Ensures unique identification of each operation, maintaining hierarchy and temporal relationships for synchronization order verification.
- **SpanContext:** Maintains data identity across different processing nodes for continuity in the Synchronization App Collector.
- **Attributes and Events:** Provide granular details about operations, aiding in detecting and contextualizing synchronization anomalies.
- **Links:** Correlate related operations, essential for tracing parallel synchronization paths.
- **Status:** Quickly identifies successful synchronizations from failed ones for efficient error detection.
- **SpanKind:** Understanding the role of an operation, affecting synchronization times and orders.
- **IsRecording:** Optimizes processing resources by focusing only on relevant data paths.
- **Concurrency:** Ensures accuracy in data synchronization even in complex and asynchronous systems.

Conclusion

In the quest to achieve flawless accuracy in KPI data synchronization, OpenTelemetry's tracking API provides a comprehensive toolset. Each component plays a critical role in not only identifying but also rectifying synchronization anomalies, ensuring that the derived KPIs are a true reflection of the system state.

6.1.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

As we delve deeper into the complexities of ensuring optimal performance in data synchronization, a crucial component emerges: TM Forum's end-to-end performance manager services. These services offer a variety of functionality designed to strengthen performance metrics, establish quality benchmarks, and drive real-time interventions. In the context of our synchronization application collector, the integration of these

services is critical to ensure accuracy, timely synchronization of data, and a seamless holoportation experience. In the following sections, we will explore each service's unique contribution to improving the synchronization process.

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	Within the synchronization collector context, TMF657 can be utilized to set, monitor, and enforce synchronization quality benchmarks. It ensures that synchronization processes align with predefined standards, ensuring seamless data flow without any noticeable lags or misalignments.
TMF642 Alarm API	An essential API for real-time monitoring, TMF642 is all about alerting the system to immediate issues that need attention.	In the synchronization framework, any lag, delay, or misalignment is critical. This API ensures that the moment there's a deviation from the ideal synchronization pattern, instant alerts are triggered, allowing for immediate remedial action.

Table 29. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Synchronization app collector

6.1.4 Architecture

Applications generate a multitude of telemetry data, including logs, traces, and metrics. **OpenTelemetry Collector** processes this data, standardizing and refining it for export. Once passed to **TM Forum's Performance Data Mediation and Collection**, agents shape the data to conform to Performance Manager standards and then store it in the **Performance Repository**.

Next, the Analytics & Processing Layer interprets this stored data and translates it into actionable metrics. Based on this, the system's **Alarms, Thresholds and QoS Engine** monitors anomalies, sets thresholds and calculates Quality of Service (QoS) parameters. All this knowledge is finally presented in a user-friendly format in the **Presentation & User Interface** layer and user interface.

In essence, from raw telemetry to visual information, this architecture provides a seamless flow, improving performance management in distributed systems.

Figure 8. Synchronization app collector architecture

6.2 Multi-Sensor Fusion app collector

As we explore the architecture, the Multi-Sensor Fusion app collector excels in fusing data from diverse sensors to ensure a complete and highly accurate 3D representation. The interface directly influences the crucial 3D Model Accuracy KPI, emphasizing the importance of precision in creating 3D models for an optimal user experience.

6.2.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

Harnessing the capabilities of OpenTelemetry Metrics API, we can derive detailed insights about the performance and precision of each sensor, ensuring their flawless integration.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Sensor Data Latency	Histogram	Time taken by each sensor's data to be processed.	Monitors latency across all sensors and alerts for any delays.
Sensor Fusion Accuracy	Gauge	Percentage of data that gets accurately fused without discrepancies.	Validates the overall fusion process's accuracy.

Table 30. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Multi-Sensor Fusion app collector

6.2.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

The complexity of fusing data from many sensors in real time requires a sophisticated tracking system. The OpenTelemetry Tracing API is essential in this regard, providing an integrated approach to track every piece of data from every sensor along its path, ensuring accurate fusion.

- **Span:** Ensures unique identification of each operation, maintaining hierarchy and temporal relationships for synchronization order verification.
- **SpanContext:** Maintains data identity across different processing nodes for continuity in the Synchronization App Collector.
- **Attributes and Events:** Provide granular details about operations, aiding in detecting and contextualizing synchronization anomalies.
- **Links:** Correlate related operations, essential for tracing parallel synchronization paths.
- **Status:** Quickly identifies successful synchronizations from failed ones for efficient error detection.
- **SpanKind:** Understanding the role of an operation, affecting synchronization times and orders.
- **IsRecording:** Optimizes processing resources by focusing only on relevant data paths.
- **Concurrency:** Ensures accuracy in data synchronization even in complex and asynchronous systems.

Conclusion

In the realm of multi-sensor fusion, the OpenTelemetry Tracing API offers a sophisticated toolset. From tracing the lineage of each piece of data, understanding its relationship to other data streams, to ensuring its accurate integration into the final 3D model, each component of the Tracing API plays a critical role. This ensures that the 3D models created are not only complete, but also maintain the highest fidelity and accuracy.

6.2.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

The integration of data from multiple sensors, each with its nuances and specifications, demands an evolved performance management mechanism. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager services become a backbone of this architecture. These services ensure that the fusion process aligns with industry best practices, quality benchmarks are met, and real-time interventions take place. An exploration of each of these services and their applications is provided below:

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	In the realm of multi-sensor fusion, TMF657 is leveraged to define and monitor the quality of the data received from each sensor. By establishing quantifiable benchmarks, this API ensures the integrity and accuracy of the data from each sensor, paving the way for an accurate 3D model.
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Given the critical nature of accurate data fusion, TMF649 defines specific thresholds for each sensor's data. If any sensor data deviates from these defined metrics, indicating potential fusion errors, alerts are generated instantly, allowing for real-time corrections.

Table 31. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Multi-sensor Fusion app collector

6.2.4 Architecture

Sensors contribute telemetry data, processed by OpenTelemetry Collector and refined by TM Forum's Performance Data Mediation. The Analysis & Processing Layer interprets data, maintaining 3D model fidelity, while alarms, thresholds, and QoS engine ensure high-quality representations. The Presentation layer provides an intuitive interface.

6.3 Volumetric Video Encoding app collector

The Volumetric Video Encoding app collector is a pivotal component ensuring superior holoport content quality. The related KPI, Volumetric Video Encoding Efficiency, underscores the importance of efficient video encoding for real-time streaming and optimal user experiences. OpenTelemetry's integration provides invaluable tracking capabilities, allowing granular observation of the encoding process. Complemented by TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager, which offers benchmarks for modern digital experiences, this architecture ensures excellence in volumetric video encoding.

6.3.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

To ensure optimal video encoding, understanding, and monitoring the process becomes paramount. The **OpenTelemetry Metrics API** comes into play, offering a wide range of metrics that provide insight into the performance of the encoding process.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Encoding Delay	Histogram	Time taken to encode a specific volume of video data.	Monitors encoding speeds and alerts for any delays.
Buffer Underflow Rate	Counter	Number of times the playback buffer runs out of content because of encoding delays.	Ensures continuous playback without buffering issues.

Table 32. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Volumetric Video Encoding app collector

6.3.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

In the world of video encoding, understanding the flow of each operation and the relationships between them is vital. The OpenTelemetry Tracing API presents essential tools to ensure transparency throughout the encoding process.

- **Span and SpanContext:** Captures individual encoding operations, allowing step-by-step identification for efficient and error-free coding processes.
- **Attributes and Events:** Provides detailed insights into each coding operation, highlighting anomalies, deviations, or important milestones.
- **Links:** Ensures capture of dependencies in a complex coding system, ensuring end-to-end traceability.
- **Status:** Quickly differentiates between successful and unsuccessful coding operations, acting as a checkpoint for coding quality.
- **SpanKind:** Identifies whether data is being processed, produced, or consumed, providing insight into overall coding efficiency and potential bottlenecks.
- **IsRecording:** Optimizes resources by tracking only relevant encoding paths, eliminating unnecessary tracking of all processes.
- **Concurrency:** Maintains the integrity of encoding processes even during parallel tasks, ensuring the reliability of operations.

Conclusion

Ensuring optimal volumetric video encoding is a nuanced task that requires an impeccable combination of monitoring, real-time feedback, and performance benchmarks. OpenTelemetry's metrics and tracking capabilities are critical to achieving this. Through its rich tracking and metrics capabilities, we gain valuable insight into the coding process, helping to identify and address inefficiencies. This meticulous monitoring ensures that our encoding process is not only streamlined but also results in consistently high-quality airport content.

6.3.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

TM Forum's services become critical to ensure that volumetric video encoding aligns with global standards and benchmarks. Its range of services focuses specifically on performance, quality and responsiveness, all of which are vital for efficient video encoding.

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	Establishes and monitors video encoding quality benchmarks, ensuring that each encoded video aligns with predefined quality standards.
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Sets specific thresholds for encoding processes, alerting if any deviations occur, indicating potential inefficiencies or problems.

Table 33. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Volumetric Video Encoding app collector

Ensuring optimal volumetric video encoding requires a seamless combination of monitoring, real-time feedback and performance benchmarks. By leveraging OpenTelemetry's rich monitoring and metrics capabilities, coupled with TM Forum's world-renowned performance management services, we ensure that our encoding process remains world-class. This complex system ensures that volumetric encoding of video data is not only efficient but also consistently delivers high-quality holoport content.

6.3.4 Architecture

The volumetric video encoding application compiler processes data seamlessly, with OpenTelemetry agents capturing telemetry data during encoding. This data flows through OpenTelemetry Collector to TM Forum's performance data collection layer, where it is matched to Performance Manager standards. Analyzed in the Processing layer, insights trigger alerts or interventions. The Presentation and User Interface layer presents coding metrics, offering a clear view of the efficiency and quality of the process.

6.4 Transport collector

The Transport Collector is pivotal for ensuring ultra-low latency in real-time holoportation, emphasizing the importance of the Latency Key Performance Indicator (KPI). The OpenTelemetry Metrics API and Tracing API play crucial roles in achieving flawless transportation.

6.4.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

To achieve flawless transportation, continuous monitoring and understanding of the process is critical. **OpenTelemetry Metrics API** offers a comprehensive set of metrics that provide a bird's eye view of transport performance.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Packet Latency	Histogram	Time taken for a data packet to traverse from its origin to its destination.	Ensures minimal delay in data transmission.
Packet Delivery Rate	Counter	Number of packets successfully reaching the destination.	Monitors successful data deliveries ensuring integrity.

Table 34. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Transport collector

6.4.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

In the field of data transport, visibility into the path of each operation and the intricate relationships between them is of paramount importance. The OpenTelemetry Tracing API provides tools that ensure end-to-end visibility throughout the entire transport process.

- **Span and SpanContext:**
 - Delimits individual data transmission operations, crucial for identifying inefficiencies or disruptions in the transport path.
 - SpanContext maintains lineage, especially when a data packet traverses multiple nodes or hops.
- **Attributes and Events:**
 - Attributes offer in-depth information about each transmission operation, capturing nuances like network type, packet size, and associated errors.
 - Events mark important milestones or deviations, ensuring real-time feedback on the transport process.
- **Links:** Weaves together multiple interconnected data streams, ensuring complete traceability in the intertwined nature of network operations.
- **Status:** Acts as a quick diagnostic tool, differentiating successful data transmissions from those encountering problems.
- **SpanKind:** Identifies the nature of transport (incoming, outgoing, or internal data), providing insight into overall transport efficiency.
- **IsRecording:** Ensures wise resource allocation by focusing only on crucial paths, optimizing performance, and reducing unnecessary overhead in the vast universe of data transmission.
- **Concurrency:** Maintains data integrity and order during simultaneous transmissions in the transport layer, ensuring efficient handling without overlap or data loss.

Conclusion

Achieving low latency in real-time holoportation is akin to orchestrating a symphony with numerous instruments. Every note, or in this case every packet of data, must be perfect and timely. OpenTelemetry's tracking API provides the conductor's baton, ensuring that every part of the transport process runs in harmony. From understanding the path of each packet with Spans and SpanContexts to monitoring anomalies with Attributes and Events, and ensuring resource optimization with IsRecording, the API provides a complete toolset. And with features such as Links and Concurrency, it

ensures that the entire orchestra, no matter how complex the composition, produces a flawless performance.

6.4.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

Given the critical nature of low latency in holoportation, it is essential that our transport operations meet the gold standard. TM Forum's suite of services ensures this alignment, providing a solid foundation for our transport operations.

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	Acts as the beacon for transport quality, ensuring consistent adherence to the highest standards.
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Sets a clear bar for transport operations, alerting when deviations occur, signaling potential challenges.

Table 35. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Transport collector

6.4.4 Architecture

The transport collector, designed for efficient data packet transport, utilizes OpenTelemetry agents strategically placed to monitor and capture telemetry data. OpenTelemetry Collector processes this data, aligning it with Performance Manager standards, and TM Forum's layer stores it in the performance repository. The analysis and processing layer optimizes transport efficiency and latency, guiding real-time decisions through alarms, thresholds, and the QoS engine. The end user receives a presentation through the User Interface layer, ensuring that from packet generation to arrival, the process aligns with the highest standards, guaranteeing ultra-low latency for holoportation.

6.5 Network collector

The Network Collector takes center stage in ensuring the vitality of our holoportation system by overseeing the smooth and efficient transmission of data. The Bandwidth Utilization Key Performance Indicator (KPI) stands as a beacon, quantifying the effectiveness of our data transport mechanism.

6.5.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

To measure the efficiency and health of our network, it is critical to have access to relevant metrics. **OpenTelemetry's metrics API** provides invaluable data to evaluate and optimize network performance.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Bandwidth Utilization	Gauge	Measures the amount of used bandwidth versus available bandwidth.	Monitors network efficiency and helps optimize data flow.
Packet Loss Rate	Counter	Number of data packets lost during transmission.	Ensures data integrity and prompts action when packet loss is high.

Table 36. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Network collector

6.5.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

A comprehensive understanding of each network operation is critical. The **OpenTelemetry Tracing API** plays a vital role by providing granular information about every transaction in the network.

- **Span and SpanContext:**
 - Views each transmitted packet as a span, making it traceable through the network maze.
 - SpanContext ensures continuity, even when packets traverse multiple nodes or paths.
- **Attributes and Events:** Provides detailed information about each network operation, highlighting anomalies, bottlenecks, or important milestones in the transmission process.
- **Links:** Ensures the capture of dependencies in branching or reliant network operations, offering a holistic view of the entire transmission process.
- **Status:** Acts as an instant checkpoint for network integrity, enabling quick identification of successful transmissions from failed ones.
- **SpanKind:** Distinguishes between sent, received, or internally processed data, facilitating a clearer understanding of network traffic flow and potential hotspots.
- **IsRecording:** Ensures judicious resource allocation amidst constant data transmission, focusing only on important transmission paths.
- **Concurrency:** Maintains data integrity for each packet, even during simultaneous transactions in the network, ensuring efficient handling without compromising data integrity.

Conclusion

Ensuring robust network performance in a holoport configuration requires an orchestra of finely tuned instruments. OpenTelemetry's tracking API acts as a conductor, harmonizing every network transaction. From tracking individual packets with Spans and SpanContexts to optimizing resource allocation with IsRecording, it ensures flawless performance, crucial for an unparalleled holoportation experience.

6.5.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

Given the critical nature of low latency in holoportation, it is essential that our transport operations meet the gold standard. TM Forum's suite of services ensures this alignment, providing a solid foundation for our transport operations.

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	Sets and monitors network performance benchmarks.
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Alerts are generated if network performance deviates from set benchmarks.

Table 37. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Network collector

6.5.4 Architecture

At the heart of our holoport infrastructure, the Network Collector, equipped with sensors and agents, captures real-time metrics related to bandwidth, latency, packet loss, and more. OpenTelemetry agents strategically placed in the network collect telemetry data, routed to the OpenTelemetry Collector for processing. Processed data aligns with TM Forum standards, stored in the Performance Repository. The analysis and processing layer decodes data, generating actionable information. Alarms, Thresholds, and the QoS engine intervene in case of anomalies, with the Presentation and User Interface layer providing a user-friendly representation. The synergy between OpenTelemetry and TM Forum ensures unparalleled network efficiency, fundamental for a seamless holoport experience.

6.6 Platform collector

In the core layers of our holoportation ecosystem, the Platform Collector ensures the robustness and efficiency of the platform, vital for sustaining services. The Resource Allocation Efficiency KPI quantifies the capacity with which system resources are allocated and employed.

6.6.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

To ensure the health and efficiency of the platform, OpenTelemetry's metrics API provides a detailed variety of metrics that shed light on various facets of the platform's operations.

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
CPU Utilization	Gauge	Percentage of CPU being used.	Identifies CPU usage patterns and potential bottlenecks.
Memory Usage	Gauge	Memory being consumed by processes.	Monitors for potential memory leaks or overutilization.

Table 38. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Platform collector

6.6.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

For deep visibility into platform operations, the OpenTelemetry tracking API becomes essential.

- **Span and SpanContext:** Encapsulate platform operations, ensuring traceability and continuity between interlocking operations.
- **Attributes and events:** Detailing specific aspects of operations, they illuminate anomalies and important occurrences within platform processes.
- **Links:** Providing a complete snapshot of dependent operations, ensuring seamless traceability between interlocking tasks.
- **Status:** Distinguishes between fluid and potentially compromised operations, acting as a barometer of platform status.
- **SpanKind:** Segregates operations according to their nature, providing insight into internal workflows.
- **IsRecording:** Focuses resources by highlighting operations of importance, ensuring efficiency.
- **Concurrency:** Maintains data consistency during simultaneous operations, ensuring platform consistency.

Conclusion

The meticulous art of platform management demands unparalleled visibility and optimization. OpenTelemetry's tracking API is a model in this effort and offers a clear path to efficient platform operations and resource allocation.

6.6.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

TM Forum services set the benchmarks for platform performance and resource utilization.

API	Description	Application
TMF657 Service Quality Management API	This API enables the extraction of Service Level Specifications (SLS) and the associated Service Level Objectives (SLO) along with their thresholds. It essentially facilitates access to quality standards that services must adhere to.	Establishes and supervises platform performance metrics.
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Sets the benchmarks and alerts when deviations are observed.

Table 39. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Platform collector

6.6.4 Architecture

The Platform Collector, deeply integrated into the holoport ecosystem, continuously captures system metrics. OpenTelemetry agents channel telemetry data points to the OpenTelemetry Collector, where data is refined and prepared for export. This refined data aligns with TM Forum standards through the performance data collection and mediation layer, reaching the Performance Repository. The analysis and processing layer discerns deviations, triggering necessary alerts or adjustments through the Alarms, Thresholds, and QoS engine. The Presentation and User Interface layer summarizes the platform's performance, creating an optimized process for platform health.

6.7 Alarm services

In the dynamic landscape of holoportation, Alarm Services act as the first line of defense, monitoring system health through the Quality of Experience (QoE) KPI. This KPI guarantees high user satisfaction by responding in real-time to any deviations from the benchmark.

6.7.1 OpenTelemetry Metrics API

To provide real-time feedback on system status and performance, OpenTelemetry's metrics API is essential. Here is a set of detailed metrics specific to alarm services:

Metric	Instrument	Description	Application
Threshold Breaches	Counter	Number of times a KPI crosses its set threshold.	Monitors system stability and alerts on potential issues.
Alarm Activation Rate	Counter	Rate at which alarms are activated.	Measures system's responsiveness to detected anomalies.

Table 40. OpenTelemetry Metrics API for Alarm services

6.7.2 OpenTelemetry Tracing API

Understanding the intricate cascade of events that lead to an alarm becomes essential. OpenTelemetry's tracking API sheds light on this:

- **Span and SpanContext:** Each event that triggers an alarm is traced back to its source, enabling root cause analysis.
- **Attributes and events:** Provide detailed context about the operation that triggers the alarm, from the triggering event to its resolution.
- **Links:** Provides a comprehensive trace of dependent operations that could contribute to generating an alarm.
- **Status:** Indicates whether the alarm-triggering operation was successful or encountered problems.
- **SpanKind:** Differentiates between various operations, highlighting those that frequently contribute to generating alarms.
- **IsRecording:** Ensures optimal use of resources by focusing on important alarm-related operations.
- **Concurrency:** Ensures consistent tracking of concurrent operations, especially in multiple sub-process alarm scenarios.

Conclusion

Achieving optimal QoE requires a meticulous and efficient alarming mechanism. OpenTelemetry's monitoring API provides valuable insight into the complexities of alarm services, ensuring fast response and rectification.

6.7.3 TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services

TM Forum's services shape the alarm system to align with global best practices, ensuring a world-class response mechanism.

API	Description	Application
TMF649 Performance Thresholding API	This API is central to the creation, retrieval, modification, and deletion of performance thresholds. It also offers the ability to initiate threshold jobs and get notifications when thresholds are crossed.	Sets the benchmarks and alerts when deviations are observed.
TMF642 Alarm API	An essential API for real-time monitoring, TMF642 is all about alerting the system to immediate issues that need attention.	Ensures instant notifications on resource or platform anomalies.

Table 41. TM Forum's End-to-End Performance Manager Services for Alarm services

6.7.4 Architecture

The Alarm Services architecture is seamlessly woven into the fabric of the holoport ecosystem. Continuous data capture of system metrics is ensured by the Platform Collector. OpenTelemetry agents channel telemetry data points to the OpenTelemetry Collector, refining and preparing the data for export. This refined data is aligned with TM Forum standards through the performance data collection and mediation layer, reaching the Performance Repository. The analysis and processing layer discerns deviations, triggering necessary alerts or adjustments through the Alarms, Thresholds, and QoS engine. Finally, the Presentation and User Interface layer provides a comprehensive overview of the platform's performance, culminating in an optimized process for sustained platform health.

6.8 Analytics services

Acting as the analytical brain, the analysis services process telemetry data and provide an overview of all KPIs. The insights and assessments of this service form the basis for numerous decisions and underline its importance throughout the system.

6.8.1 Overview

The analytics services are structured to seamlessly ingest, process, and visualize telemetry data. At the heart of these services is the analytical processing engine, which orchestrates the harmonious flow of data through various modules, ensuring that real-time insights are gained efficiently. The resource allocation efficiency KPI is a testament to this efficiency, as it measures the optimal use of system resources.

6.8.2 Architecture

Figure 9. Analytics services architecture

The architecture of our Analysis Services is modular, and each module serves specific functionalities:

- **Data Ingestion Layer:** Acts as an entry point for telemetry data. Integrated with OpenTelemetry Collector, it is adept at managing real-time data streams, batch processing data and authenticating ingested data, preparing it for further analysis.
- **Analytical Processing Engine:** The fundamental point, this engine channels data analysis. It is enhanced with the Query Processor to handle data queries, the Aggregation Module for data collection and the Temporal Analyzer to decipher time-bound patterns.
- **Data Processing Pipelines:** at this point, data undergoes detailed processing. Map-Reduce tasks distill large segments of data, while in-memory computing ensures fast access to the data. The crown jewel, the Insights Generation Mechanism, leverages pattern recognition, statistical evaluation, and predictive analytics to extract important insights from raw data.
- **Database Systems:** By anchoring analysis operations, this module ensures optimized storage and retrieval operations of processed data. The time series database efficiently stores chronological data, while the data indexing component ensures fast and accurate data retrieval.

6.8.3 Proposal Technologies

- **Pattern recognition:** We have identified **TensorFlow** as a leading technology because of its scalability and extensive tools. However, **PyTorch** is also a strong contender, especially with its dynamic computational graph, which offers flexibility in building analytical models.
- **Time series database:** We propose to use **TimescaleDB**. It is a SQL-based database, which provides the familiarity of SQL and, at the same time, is specifically optimized for time series data, which facilitates data management

and querying. An alternative could be **InfluxDB**, known for its high write and query speeds.

- **Dashboard Generator:** Grafana stands out as our primary visualization tool due to its seamless integration capabilities with a variety of data sources and his good intregation with **Prometheus**. On the other hand, **Tableau**, with its intuitive interface and extensive visualization tools, is also a solid alternative that we consider or even ELK Stack.
- **Data ingestion: OpenTelemetry** remains our top choice for the data ingestion layer. It is a CNCF project with broad community support, offering comprehensive tools for end-to-end telemetry data collection and processing.

6.8.4 Adapting to KPIs and Telemetry Data

The platform's dynamic KPIs demand a flexible analytical approach. By incorporating machine learning models, Analytics Services adapt to evolving data patterns, ensuring accurate KPI assessments. OpenTelemetry facilitates real-time telemetry data collection for up-to-date analysis.

6.8.5 Role in decision making

The insights generated by Analysis Services play a critical role in strategic and operational decisions. By constantly tracking KPI performance and predicting potential bottlenecks or inefficiencies, the service equips decision makers with actionable intelligence. Whether to optimize resource allocation, improve user experience or preventively addresssing system issues, analytics services act as a guiding light.

6.8.6 Integration with Third-Party AI Modules

An integral aspect of this functionality lies in the potential collaboration with third-party AI modules developed in parallel tasks of the project.

- **Exploiting Monitoring Measures:** The telemetry data, being the lifeline of the holoportation ecosystem, serves as a rich source for AI-driven insights. Third-party AI modules, developed as part of other project tasks, can seamlessly integrate with our Analytics Services to harness the wealth of monitoring measures. This integration opens avenues for leveraging advanced AI algorithms, machine learning models, and pattern recognition techniques to extract deeper insights from the telemetry data.
- **Utilizing TensorFlow and PyTorch:** For instance, by interfacing with TensorFlow or PyTorch, leading technologies in pattern recognition, our analytics services can tap into the scalability and flexibility offered by these frameworks. These AI modules can dynamically adapt to evolving data patterns, enhancing the accuracy of KPI assessments, and providing a more nuanced understanding of system performance.
- **Real-Time Telemetry Data Collection:** OpenTelemetry, as our preferred choice for real-time telemetry data collection, ensures that Analytics Services always operates with up-to-date data. This, in turn, enhances the capabilities of third-party AI modules, allowing them to make informed decisions based on the most recent telemetry insights.
- **Decision-Making Empowerment:** The insights generated by the collaborative efforts of Analytics Services and third-party AI modules play a crucial role in strategic and operational decisions. Whether it's optimizing resource allocation,

improving user experience, or proactively addressing potential system issues, this amalgamation of monitoring measures and advanced AI capabilities serves as a powerful tool for decision-makers.

6.8.7 Conclusion

Analytics Services, with its robust architecture and state-of-the-art technologies, ensures that every piece of telemetry data is transformed into actionable information. As the backbone of the system, it continually refines its analytical models to reflect the changing nature of KPIs, solidifying its position as an indispensable entity in the decision-making process. By translating raw data into meaningful information, the service promises an optimized, efficient, and proactive system environment.

6.9 KPI & Metrics Manager services

Finally, KPI & Metrics Manager services ensure that all performance metrics and KPIs are not only managed but also presented in a way that aligns with established objectives. This service acts as the final sentinel, ensuring that system performance consistently resonates with defined standards.

6.9.1 Overview

Strategically placed within the ecosystem, KPI & Metrics Manager Services serve as a conduit, seamlessly interacting between raw telemetry data from various collectors, processed insights from analytics services, and final representation to stakeholders.

Figure 10. KPI & Metrics Manager services architecture

6.9.2 Architecture integration

Intertwined within the broader architecture of analytics services, KPI & Metrics Manager integrates with both the data processing channels and the visualization and alerting layer:

- **KPI Registry:** Hosts a dynamic catalog of all active KPIs. It interacts with the data ingestion layer, ensuring that each telemetry data finds its corresponding KPI.
- **Metrics Aggregator:** This module, closely aligned with the analytical processing engine, groups metrics from all corners and presents a unified view without redundancies.
- **Performance Benchmark Comparator:** Linked to the analytics and processing layer, it contrasts live KPI values against established benchmarks, highlighting any deviations or areas that need attention.
- **Visualization Enhancer:** dovetails with the visualization and alerting layer, adjusting the representation of KPIs to ensure that stakeholders can intuitively understand even the most complex metrics.

6.9.3 Integration with Collectors and Services

Each collector, whether Platform Collector, Network Collector or any other, enters the KPI & Metrics Manager. The raw data is channeled through OpenTelemetry, ensuring its standardization before being processed. Once processed, these refined metrics are presented through services such as alarm and analysis services, ensuring that stakeholders always have an overview of system performance.

6.9.4 Role in decision making

By providing a panoramic view of all KPIs, the KPI & Metrics Manager becomes the fulcrum for strategic decisions. Whether it is adjusting resources based on Platform Collector's insights or modifying the network configuration thanks to Network Collector's feedback, decisions are data-driven, accurate and timely.

6.9.5 Conclusion

In the vast constellation of modules, collectors and services, KPI & Metrics Manager Services emerges as the guiding star, ensuring clarity amidst complexity. By ensuring that every piece of data is properly accounted for, analyzed and represented, it reaffirms our commitment to excellence and continuous improvement in holoportation.

7 Conclusion

In our journey through the intricate intricacies of holoportation, several fundamental conclusions have crystallized. The development of this article not only solidified my understanding of the technical complexities, but also underscored the profound impact of fusion technology with user-centric principles.

1. **Integrated architecture is crucial:** a cohesive architecture that integrates multiple facets (synchronization, multi-sensor fusion, volumetric video encoding, network management, and platform state) is essential. As we dissected each component, it became clear that excellence in isolation is insufficient; the synergy of these components determines the holistic holoportation experience.
2. **Telemetry is the lifeline:** OpenTelemetry's capabilities, particularly its metrics and tracking APIs, emerged as the backbone of real-time monitoring. The granularity and adaptability they offer have proven indispensable for identifying inefficiencies and ensuring optimal performance across the board.
3. **Benchmarking elevates performance:** The inclusion of TM Forum's end-to-end performance management services highlighted the value of global standards and benchmarks. Performance is not just about speed or efficiency, but about aligning with industry best practices to ensure consistency and reliability.
4. **User experience is paramount:** regardless of technological prowess, the ultimate litmus test lies in quality of experience (QoE). Our deep dive into alarm services reiterated the importance of proactive monitoring and real-time interventions. Ensuring that anomalies do not degrade the user experience is as crucial as the innovations that drive the holoportation experience.
5. **Flexibility and adaptability are key:** As the paper developed, one principle constantly resonated: the need for adaptability. Whether it is adapting to new synchronization challenges, evolving sensor data, or refining coding techniques, adaptability is intrinsic to maintaining and enhancing the holoportation experience.

Reflecting on the totality of this research, while we have made significant advances in holoportation technology, the road ahead is full of possibilities. The balance between intricate technical orchestration and user-centered design will be the guiding light. As an architect, the journey of writing this article has reinforced my belief in the confluence of technology and human-centered design, propelling us into a future where distances diminish, and experiences become increasingly immersive.